

AUTOMATED FEATURE BASED DETECTION AND PREDICTION METHODS FOR RICE DISEASES USING DEEP NEURAL NETWORKS

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Abstract

Crop diseases have serious economic impacts if not detected at an early stage. Rice is an important cash crop in Asia and is the backbone of the economy of many countries. Therefore, accurate and rapid detection of plant diseases is critical, but a difficult task. Brown spots, leafblast and Hispa are common diseases of rice plants that are visible to the human eye. However, it takes time to manually inspect/detect a large field and cannot prevent the rapid spread of the disease. Deep learning provides accurate, fast, and independent detection and recognition through image classification. This research work proposes Deep Learning algorithms to detect rice diseases. A rice dataset used in this work is based on four labelled rice classes out of which three (Brownspot, Leafblast, Hispa) are diseased and one is healthy (having healthy leaf images). This research work is divided into two parts, A comparative analysis of pre-trained deep learning models which comprises VGG16, VGG19, InceptionV3 and ResNet50. VGG16 reached the highest accuracy 94% of the benchmarking. secondly, two models Stacked Convolve Neural Network (SCNN) and Dense Classified Neural Network (DCNN) are offered for detection and classification purposes. SCNN achieves 98% precision while DCNN achieves 99.96% drive precision.

Introduction

The agriculture sector plays a vital role in the economy of a country. Rice (*Oryza Sativa*) is an important staple food being used by the 3.5 billion individuals all over the world. 90% of the rice is being produced and

used in Asia and 10% is being produced outside Asia. In Asia almost 11 countries are liable for rice production out of which two countries China and India, have their major part making 37% of the total population of the world while

globally their production for rice is 49% [1, 2, 3]. Similarly, Pakistan is an agricultural country and its economy depends largely on agriculture, almost 42.3% of total population is associated with agriculture domain.

Wheat is the largest contributing crop of Pakistan followed by Rice that contributes almost 18.9% of total GDP [4, 5]. The average rice yield is reduced due to different factors such as environmental factors such as climate change which reduce the yield up to 70%, temperature, water availability due to this productivity of crops loss about 30-70% and air pollution in which diseases is one of the major factors which causes yield loss up to 30 to 100. Rice diseases and pest affect the quality and productivity of plant that may appear at any developmental stage of the plant [6, 7]. Moreover, any part of plant such as leaf, seed, root, and stem can be affected while fungi, bacteria and viruses can be the cause of disease. With rapidly increasing population, food requirements also rise but agricultural field is facing many challenges such as crop diseases, environmental factors and loss in productivity etc. With the swift increase in technology, disease detection and analysis using image processing provides better results. But the accuracy still depends on the number and quality of images, features extraction and then classification. The advances in deep learning significantly increased the efficiency of classification tasks and have produced more reliable results. In the domain of agriculture, deep learning is being applied for various purposes [8, 9] such as to separate the weed from plants using image recognition and identification using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN). In this research rice plant's disease classification using deep learning models is presented. Three different diseases namely Brown spot, Leaf Blast, pest class (Hispa) are differentiated from healthy leaves. Four different techniques

are employed to have more reliable outcome and improved accuracy. Section 2 provides review of already proposed methods for identifying diseases from images and the development in machine learning and deep learning methods. Section 3 details the materials and methods used in this study followed by

data description in section 4. The results are discussed in section 7 and finally the concluding remarks are given in section 8.

2. Related Work

By using Convolutional Neural Networks [10] recognized soybean leaf diseases. 1470 soybean images and three pre-trained CNN models named GoogLeNet, AlexNet and ResNet were used for this purpose. The parameters of ResNet were optimized to enhance performance, accomplishing accuracy of 95.78. [11, 12] proposed machine learning algorithm to find symptoms of diseases in rice plants and automatically detect rice blast disease. 300 images were captured from paddy leaf fields. GLCM was used for the extraction of textural features while ANN was used as classifier and achieved training accuracy of 99% while 90% of testing accuracy. [13] diagnose and detect the rice leaf diseases. SIFT was used to detect feature of the images and convert them into words by using BoW (Bag of Words) technique. SVM parameters were optimized to achieve high efficiency and accomplished 94.14% accuracy. [14] measured the severity of rice disease by using K-mean segmentation and used fuzzy logic and different machine vision methods to predict the severity of disease. Image segmentation was done by K-mean algorithm, while GLCM was used for extract the features. SVM was used for classification attaining accuracy of 86.35%. Though, valuable and considerable research has been conducted in disease and pest detection of crops using images but the features extraction in images is notable constraint while dealing with SVM, KNN or K-means algorithms [15]. With the advancements of deep learning algorithms, automated diseases and pests detection is carried out in rice crops. Deep learning algorithms automatically extract the features. Researchers has analyzed initially developed deep learning algorithms like AlexNet, over field and LeNet on small datasets consisted 200, 300 and 600 images [16]. Deep learning is also applied for the classification of lands for different purposes such as to differentiate urban land, agriculture land, forest land etc. [17, 18] performed

item detection and identification in cultivating crops using deep learning. Moreover, weather prediction is also determined using deep learning [19]. Deep learning has made yield prediction easier in agriculture, it can be used for the classification of animal behaviors [20]. Moreover, deep learning is also being used in agriculture for species recognition [21], pest detection [22], crop classification [19], water management [23], soil moisture management [24] and livestock management [25]. Deep learning algorithms such as CNN and its architectures such as VGG, ResNet, Inception, Xception. and RCNN also serve

for disease detection and prediction [26, 27]. In recent, deep learning algorithms such as RCNN and YOLO use regions to localize objects in the image but did not achieve good accuracy on small datasets. Continuous work is being done to overcome the problems like manual feature extraction, small datasets and large number of learning parameters, many new algorithms are formulated by researchers to fix such problems. So, there is sufficient room for improvement using recent deep learning algorithms to test performance[28].

Table 1: List of significant research that has been done in the field of agriculture for plant disease identification using deep learning and machine learning technologies.

Reference	Images	Crop	Algorithms	Accuracy
Masood et al. (2020)	1700	Rice	Mask R-CNN	87.60%
Ahmed et al. (2020)	200	Rice	Faster RCNN for image segmentation and CNN	88.07%
Agarwal et al. (2020)	17,500	Tomato	Modified CNN	91.20%
Xiong et al. (2020)	360	Green Mango	UAV using YOLOv2	86.40%
He et al. (2020)	200	Rice	Two-layer detection algorithm with YOLO v3	94.64%
Ramesh, S. (2019)	300	Rice	K-mean clustering, GLCM, ANN	90%
Bashir et al. (2019)	400	Rice	SIFT, SVM	94.14%
Militante et al. (2019)	940	Sugarcane	VGG-19, Resnet-34, Resnet-50 for classification and YOLOv3 & Faster-CNN for Identification	93.20%
Nagasubramanian et al.(2019)	1823	Soybean	3D CNN	95.73%
Ozguven & Adem (2019)	155	Sugar beet	updated faster RCNN	95.48%
S.Zhang et al. (2019)	600	Cucumber	Global pooling dilated convolutional neural network (GPDCNN)	94.65%
Geetharamani & J (2019)	55,636	Various Plant leaves	DCNN	96.46%
Khamparia et al.	600	Kharif crops	Supervised Deep CNN	93.70%

Reference	Images	Crop	Algorithms	Accuracy
(2019)				
Ferentinos (2018)	87,848	Different Plants	5 CNN models Over field, AlexNetOWTbn, GoogLeNet, AlexNet and VGG	99.53%
Din et al. (2018)	200	Tomato	GLCM, Multi-thresholding, SVM	98.30%
Ali et al. (2017)	199	Citrus	fine KNN, bagged tree, boosted tree and cubic SVM	99.50%

In this research a comparative analysis of four different models based on CNN is presented and two algorithms SCNN and DCNN for rice disease detection and classification are proposed. Less learning parameters are used in this research and all-important features are extracted manually and have labelled balanced Dataset containing more than three images taken from Kaggle's website after that data augmentation is performed to increase the size of dataset up to 11600. Firstly, this research analyzed and conducted different deep learning models such as VGG16, VGG19, ResNet-50 and InceptionV3 to compare the performance of selected algorithms on rice dataset. The second part proposed two algorithms named SCNN and DCNN for rice disease detection and classification. Both algorithms accurately detect and classify the diseases and achieved highest accuracy among all the algorithms used in literature review.

$$F_k = (I(x,y) * K_k) \quad (1)$$

Input image is represented by $I(x, y)$, x, y demonstrate spatial positions

And K_k shows the z th and convolutional kernel of k th layer. Pooling layer reduces the dimensionality of features taken out by convolutional layer also reduces number of parameters, weights, training time, competition cost and control over fitting as well. According to the type of pooling filter of 2×2 is applied to get output. There is either max pooling or average pooling, L2, overlapping etc. are used in CNN [31].

3. Materials and Methods

3.1. Convolutional Neural Network

CNNs are mathematical models that work on the imitate basis of brain functioning accompanied by neurons and synapses that unified them. It consists of three parts named as convolutional layer, pooling layer and fully connected layer [29]. First two layers together shape the feature extractor and third layer acts as a classifier. Convolution layer is a particular form of linear operations that does feature extraction where kernel is applied cross-ways the input which is the array of numbers known as tensor. Size and number of kernels define the operation, width and height of filter depends upon application, 3×3 is often used but occasionally 5×5 and 7×7 can be used as well [30]. Convolution operation can be expressed in Equation 1

$$K_z = fp(F_z) \quad (2)$$

Equation 2 demonstrates the pooling operation in which K_z represents the z th output feature map, $F(x, y)_z$ shows the z th input feature map, whereas $fp()$ denotes the type of pooling operation. Activation function act as decision function and helps to learn complex patterns.

$$A_k = f(F_k) \quad (3)$$

Convolved feature map activation function is defined in Equation 3, F_k is an output of convolution operation, which is allocated to activation function; $f_a(.)$ that add non linearity and reappearance the transformed output A_k for k th layer. Various activation functions such as sigmoid, ReLU, tenth, leaky ReLU, PReLU are used to compute combination of nonlinear feature. However, ReLU and its variations are favored over others activations as it helps in overcoming the vanishing gradient problem [32]. Dropout introduce regularization within network,

which ultimately improve generalization by randomly skipping connections with a certain probability. Multiple connections that learn a non-linear relation are sometime coadaptive which cause overfitting. Dropout helps to reduce the overfitting problem [33]. The fully connected layer accompanied by SoftMax uses the feature extracted to classify the images. A fully connected layer is required to produce an output equal to the number of classes required as output. This layer also gives the feature vector by flattening the neurons [34].

Figure 1: Basic CNN structure

3.2. CNN Models

3.2.1. VGG16

After the success of CNNs for image recognition, a modest and active design principle was proposed by Simony et al. for CNN models. One of the models, termed as VGG was segmental in pattern of layers. VGG is 19 layers deeper than AlexNet and ZefNet. ZefNet proposed that small sized filters can enhance the performance of CNNs. VGG substituted 11×11 and 5×5 filters with 3×3 stack filter layers and

experimentally confirms that simultaneous assignment of 3×3 can prompt the effect of large size filter [29].

In VGG16 3×3 convolutional layers are used; it is a sequential convolutional neural network. In VGG16 convolutional filters get double. VGG19 is an extension of VGG16 with 19 layers [35].

3.2.2. InceptionV3

Enhanced versions of Inception V1 and V2 are

Inception V3, V4 and Inception ResNet. googLeNet first proposed the concept of “Inception” by [36]. To increase ImageNet classification accuracy Inception V3 propose in-forms to inception components. In 2016, Szegedy again improve Inception V3 and Proposed Inception V4, this syndicates Inception models with residual connections while their goal was to speed up the training of inception networks. Reducing the computational cost of deeper nets was the notion of Inception-V3 keeping the generalization same. InceptionV3 comprises of inspection blocks. Convolutional filters of many dimensions and pooling are used on the input in parallel in every inception block [36]

3.2.3. ResNet50

It is NIN known as network in network model that

depend on piles of residual units. These are the set of building blocks are used to construct networks. ResNet extension of deep Nets is proposed by [37]. For training deep Nets CNN models were transformed by ResNet, presenting the idea of residual learning in CNN and planned a well-organized procedure. ResNet won 2015-24 ILSVRC competition by proposing DCNN of 152 layers. ResNet presented fewer computational complexities than former Nets because it is 20 and 8 times deeper than AlexNet and VGG. experimentally exhibits les faults on image classification by the use of ResNet with 50/101/125 layers than 34 layers . ResNet50 apart from the direct connection from the in-stant previous layer, is a deep convolutional neural network that skips the connections from earlier layer [38].

Table 2: List of four state-of-the-art deep learning networks that used for comparative analysis.

Reference	Algorithm	Salient Feature	Limitations	Suitability
(Simonyan, K., & Zisserman, A. 2014)	VGG16	Fixed Size Kernels	- Consume lot of memory - More Training Time - Vanishing Gradient Problem	Yes
(Simonyan, K., & Zisserman, A. 2014)	VGG19	Fixed Size Kernels	- Consume lot of memory - More Training Time - Vanishing Gradient Problem	Yes
(He, Kaiming, et al., 2016)	ResNet50	Shortcut Connections	- Complex Architecture - ResNet depends on Batch Normalization Layer	Yes
(Szegedy, Christian, et al., 2015)	InceptionV3	Wider-Parallel Kernels	- Complex Architecture - High Computational Cost	Yes

3.3. Fine Tuning and Transfer Learning

Transfer learning is a machine learning technique while fine tuning is its concept. In transfer learning technique the knowledge obtained during the training of problem is used to train another related task [39]. In deep learning, to identify the features of task first few layers are trained while last few layers of trained network are removed during transfer learning and fresh layers are retrained for the targeted job. Fine tune learning experiments are much faster than learning from scratch but require a bit of learning yet more

accurate as compared to model trained from scratch [40, 41].

4. Data Collection

Rice disease dataset used for this research was obtained from Kaggle's website comprising on 3355 images. The images are divided into four labelled classes: i) Brown spot ii) Leaf Blast iii) pest class known as Hispa and iv) Healthy class. The sample images of brown spot, leaf blast and pest classes are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The images of diseased classes (a) Brownspot (b) Leafblast and (c) pest class Hispa

5. Data Preprocessing

According to the requirement of Deep learning algorithms such as VGG16, VGG19, ResNet50 and InceptionV3 all the RGB images are resized. Images are resized automatically computed by Python using OpenCV framework. The dataset used is in small amount and deep learning algorithms works efficiently on larger dataset therefore, to accomplish good results size of dataset

was increased by applying data augmentation techniques including rotation which includes rotating the image in any direction at different angles and generate new images random cropping some parts of image and creating subset from the main images, zooming and horizontal flipping. Manual augmentation was performed and size of dataset was increased up to 11,600 which was further divided into training and testing in the ratio 80:20.

6. Approach

Comparative analysis of four models based on CNN is conducted that was trained on 80% of dataset in ImageNet. The pre-trained models are used for binary classification on rice dataset to predict the diseases on test data and analyzed on the basis of accuracy. The two models VGG16 & VGG19 having all freeze layers except last four layers. For the flattening of output, flattening layer is used followed by dense layer that was used as output layer. Dense layer is followed by activation function ReLU whereas output layer having number of classes and SoftMax activation function while input of each layer is the output of preceding layer. Whereas, in learning parameters, Adam optimizer is used. In InceptionV3, Global average pooling layer is used as dimension reduction, freezing all the convolutional layers of the model.

Dense layer is used, followed by activation function ReLU, after dense layer dropout of 0.5 is used to prevent over fitting. Second dense layer is output layer having number of classes followed by sigmoid activation function. In ResNet50, all the convolution layers of the model are freeze, for dimension reduction global average pooling layer is used, flattening layer is used to flatten the models' output, followed by Batch Normalization layer. Two dense layers having hidden neurons in them are used each followed by ReLU and Batch Normalization. After that dropout of 0.5 is added, final output layer having number of classes followed by SoftMax activation function. Secondly, two new approaches named Stacked Convolved Neural Network (SCNN) and Dense Classify Neural Network (DCNN) are used. SCNN and DCNN are proposed for the accurate detection of rice diseases as well as classification of images into four categories.

6.1. SCNN

Stacked Convolve Neural Network SCNN based on The architecture of the model is described as:

- Convolution layer 1 → ReLU → MaxPooling →
- Convolution layer 2 → ReLU → MaxPooling →
- Convolution layer 3 → ReLU → MaxPooling →
- Convolution layer 4 → ReLU → MaxPooling →
- Flatten layer → Dropout →
- Fully connected → ReLU → Output layer → Result

CNN is proposed for the detection of rice diseases.

The images in the dataset are resized to 224 × 224. The input image of 224 × 224 are passed to the filters to generate feature maps. Four convolutional layers are added; first convolutional layer has 32 filters, second convolutional layers has 64 filters, whereas remaining two layers have 128 filters. These convolutional layers can extract all the necessary features proceeding towards pooling layer. For example model.add(layers.Conv2D(32, (3, 3), activation =r ReLU r)) and model.add(layers.MaxPool2D(2, 2)). Pooling layer performs subsampling by keeping important features. Convolutional layers are followed by Max- Pooling and ReLU activation function. Moreover, after adding flattening layer model.add(layers.Dropout(0.5)) is used to avoid over fitting. Fully connected layer is introduced and at last output layer having number of 4 classes followed by SoftMax activation function whereas as optimizer RM-Sprop is used. Architecture of SCNN shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: SCNN Architecture

6.2. DCNN

Dense Classified Neural Network (DCNN) is proposed to detect and classify rice diseases accurately based upon VGG19 architecture by replacing dense layers. Images are resized into 224 × 224. Convolutional neural networks have two parts feature extraction and classification. Convolution layers extract all the features and dense layers are used for classification. In DCNN

includetop = False so that all necessary features are extracted and all the convolutional layers are locked/freeze, trained only the layers that are the ones of the dense classifier. Flattening layer is added that converts the feature vector of shape (7, 7,512) to one dimensional array getting the value of 25088, which is then send as input toward dense layers. First three dense layers are followed by ReLU activation function and last output layer is as classifier having number of four classes with SoftMax activation function.

Adam is an optimizer that update the network weights iteratively based on training data it is the extension of stochastic gradient decent. Adam is used as learning parameter to compile the model. Architecture diagram of DCNN shown in Figure 4. The difference between these two proposed models is that SCNN is trained from scratch and DCNN is trained on only the classifying layers. Another difference is the number of parameters SCNN have slightly higher number of parameters 9,680,580 while DCNN have 2,529,504 parameters. Both models give good training and testing accuracy but DCNN outperform then SCNN. Although SCNN also give good results but model has little over fitted for the reason that of dataset because training from scratch requires huge amount of data. In the prediction part the predictor is built to predict the images of different classes both models take random batch of images from all classes and accurately predict the classes.

Figure 4: DCNN Architecture

7. Results and Discussion

Different studies have been conducted involving different types of analysis to configure the important factors for the detection of rice leaf disease at any early stages. In this study the performance of each classifier

is measured in term of accuracy, precision, recall and F1 score. The performance comparison of each classifier is discussed in the following subsections. The confusion matrix measures are expressed in Equation 4 to 6.

$$\text{Precision} = \text{TP} / (\text{TP} + \text{FP}) \tag{4}$$

$$\text{Recall} = \text{TP} / (\text{TP} + \text{FN}) \tag{5}$$

$$\text{F1 score} = (2 * \text{Precision} * \text{Recall}) / (\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}) \tag{6}$$

Where TP = true positive, FP = false positive and FN = false negative.

7.1. Results of Comparative Analysis

For the prediction of rice disease and analysis of the

given dataset, comparative analysis of four state-of-the-art deep learning models is performed. Images are resized in 224×224 for VGG 16 and VGG 19 converting them into an array. Data is taken in ratio of 80:20 out of which 80 is used for training purpose while remaining 20 is used for testing. After that comparison of deep learning models in literature review section, it was found that VGG19 accomplished training accuracy of 92.46% while accomplished testing accuracy of 90%. Whereas,

VGG16 accomplished training accuracy of 94% and accomplished testing accuracy of 93%. In InceptionV3, images were resized to 229×229 given as input accomplishing training accuracy of 83.96% and testing accuracy of 83.68%. In ResNet images are resized to 256×256 , training accuracy was 78% while testing accuracy was 77%. On the basis of this analysis VGG16 is seen as achieving highest accuracy.

The results of training and testing of comparative analysis are shown in Table 3:

Table3. Comparative Analysis of Model’s Accuracy.

Models	Training Accuracy	Testing Accuracy
ResNet50	78%	77%
InceptionV3	84%	83.68%
VGG19	92.46%	90%
VGG16	94%	93%

These results showed that VGG16 produced more accurate results among the selected models whereas for ResNet50 attain less accurate results. Accuracy and loss graph of VGG19 is shown in Fig 5(a) representing the prediction of model by using validation dataset with using the numbers of epochs by training the model. Model achieved higher training and validation accuracy by the increase in epochs. Loss graph VGG19 represent the change in values of training loss by using validation dataset with the increase in number of epochs. After using 15 epochs training loss is almost 0 and validation loss of 0.15. Accuracy of VGG16 is increasing constantly for both training and validation. After 10 epochs VGG16 achieved highest accuracy for training 94% and validation 92% shown in Fig 5(b). Training loss is 0.78% and validation loss are 0.1179%. In InceptionV3 it can be observed that on training from 60 to 65 epochs, model performed well but after that a slight fluctuation in both training and validation can be observed. After 100 epochs training loss is 46% and validation loss is 50% shown in Fig 5(c). Accuracy and loss graph of ResNet50 is shown in Fig 5(d), trained on 30 epochs show-ing increase in training accuracy with increase in epochs while the training loss decreasing

continuously and reaches on 50%. The validation accuracy is increasing but loss is decreasing. The confusion matrix results of VGG19, VGG16, InceptionV3 and ResNet50 is shown in Table 4. VGG19 truly predict 539 Brownspot images, mispredict 23 healthy and 19 leaf blast images, 497 accurately predicted healthy images, mispredicted 10 brown spot, 39 Hispa and 34 leaf blast images, 527 accurately predicted Hispa images and mispredicted 53 healthy and 2 Leafblast images while 529 accurately predicted Leafblast images and mispredicted 4 Brownspot, 42 healthy and 5 Hispa images. VGG16 correctly predicted 543 Brownspot images, mispredicted 38 healthy and 10 Leafblast images, truly predicted 504 healthy images and mispredict 14 Brownspot 36 Hispa and 26 Leafblast images, truly predicted 549 Hispa images, mispredicted 1 Brownspot, 30 healthy and 2 Leafblast images while 560 truly predicted Leafblast images, mispredicted 1 Brownspot and 19 healthy images. InceptionV3 correctly predicted 499 Brownspot images, mispredicted 43 healthy, 15 Hispa and 24 LeafBlast images, 446 truly predicted healthy images, mispredicted 10 Brownspot, 94 Hispa and 30 Leaf-blast

images, truly predicted 506 Hispa images, mispredicted 3 Brownspot, 58 healthy and 15 Leafblast images, while truly predicted 493 Leafblast images, mispredicted 24 Brownspot, 31 healthy and 32 Hispa images. ResNet50 correctly predicted (435) Brownspot images, mispredicted 62 healthy, 4 Hispa and 80 Leafblast images, truly predicted 336 healthy images, mispredicted 33 Brownspot, 73 Hispa and 139

LeafBlast images, 440 truly predict Hispa images, mispredicted 10 Brownspot, 90 healthy and 40 Leafblast images, while truly predict 528 Leafblast images, mispredicted 11 Brownspot, 35 healthy and 5 Hispa. Performance evaluation of VGG19, VGG16, InceptionV3 and ResNet50 is shown in Table 4.

Figure 5: Shows the accuracy and loss graph of VGG19 (a), VGG16 (b), InceptionV3 (c) and ResNet50 (d)

Table 4: Summarize results of Confusion Matrix of VGG19, VGG16, InceptionV3 and ResNet50.

MODEL	DISEASE	BROWNSPOT	HEALTHY	HISPA	LEAF BLAST
VGG19	BROWNSPOT	539	23	0	19
	Healthy	10	497	39	34
	Hispa	0	53	527	2
	Leaf Blast	4	42	5	529
VGG16	Brownsport	543	28	0	10
	Healthy	14	504	36	26
	Hispa	1	30	549	2
	Leaf Blast	1	19	0	560
INCEPTIONV3	Brownsport	499	43	15	24
	Healthy	10	446	94	30
	Hispa	3	58	506	15
	Leaf Blast	24	31	32	493
RESNET50	Brownsport	435	62	4	80
	Healthy	33	336	73	139
	Hispa	10	90	440	40
	Leaf Blast	11	35	5	528

Table 5: Performance evaluation of VGG19, VGG16, InceptionV3 and ResNet50

Models	DISEASES	PRECISION	RECALL	F1-SCORE	SUPPORT
VGG19	Brownsport	0.97	0.93	0.95	581
	Healthy	0.81	0.86	0.83	580
	Hispa	0.92	0.91	0.91	582
	Leafblast	0.91	0.91	0.91	580
VGG16	Brownsport	0.97	0.93	0.95	581
	Healthy	0.87	0.87	0.87	580
	Hispa	0.94	0.94	0.94	582

	Leafblast	0.94	0.97	0.95	580
InceptionV3	Brownspot	0.93	0.86	0.89	581
	Healthy	0.77	0.77	0.77	580
	Hispa	0.78	0.87	0.82	582
	Leafblast	0.88	0.85	0.86	580
ResNet50	Brownspot	0.89	0.75	0.81	581
	Healthy	0.64	0.58	0.61	580
	Hispa	0.84	0.76	0.80	582
	Leafblast	0.67	0.91	0.77	580

7.2. SCNN and DCNN Results

Dataset consisted of 11,600 images of four rice classes, 9294 of them were used for training while remaining 2323 were used for the testing. First proposed model SCNN, based on CNN achieved training accuracy of 98.11% while testing accuracy of 97.33%. Second

model DCNN, based on VGG19 achieved training accuracy of 99.88% while testing accuracy of 98.62%. Images were predicted correctly by both algorithms. The results of training and testing accuracies are shown in Table6.

Table 6: SCNN & DCNN training and testing accuracies

Models	Training Accuracy	Testing Accuracy
SCNN	98.11%	97.33%
DCNN	99.88%	98.62%

or SCNN the accuracy graph shown in Fig 6 illustrates that both training and validation accuracy of model increase continuously with increase in epochs. Training and validation loss decrease till almost 0 with the increase in epochs, slight fluctuation is observed in validation loss ultimately reaching to 0. Confusion matrix is shown in Table 6 illustrating that model correctly predicted 581 (100%) Brownspot images, truly predicted 520 (0.9%) healthy images, mispredicted 8 Brownspot, 35 Hispa and 17 Leafblast images, truly predicted 580 (100%) Hispa images, while 580 (100%) truly predict Leaf-blast images. Performance evaluation of SCNN is shown in Table 8. DCNN

model accuracy graph both training and validation accuracy is increasing with increase in epochs. The loss graph depicts that training loss decreases below zero with increase in epochs while validation loss hits zero shown in Fig 7. Confusion matrix is shown in Table 7 illustrating that model correctly predicted 581(100%) Brownspot images, truly predicted 551 healthy images, mispredicted 6 Brownspot, 17 Hispa and 6 LeafBlast images, truly predicted 582 (100%) Hispa images, while 580 (100%) truly predicted Leafblast images. Classification report/ Performance evaluation of DCNN is shown in Table 8

Figure 6: SCNN accuracy and loss graph

Figure 7: DCNN accuracy and loss graph

Table 7: Summarize results of Confusion Matrix SCNN and DCNN

Models	Labels	brownspot	healthy	Hispa	Leaf Blast
SCNN	Brownspot	581	0	0	0
	Healthy	8	520	35	17
	Hispa	0	2	580	0
	Leafblast	0	0	0	580
DCNN	Brownspot	581	0	0	0
	Healthy	6	551	17	6
	Hispa	0	0	582	0
	Leafblast	0	0	0	580

Table 8: Performance evaluation of SCNN and DCNN

Models	DISEASES	PRECISION	RECALL	F1-SCORE	SUPPORT
SCNN	Brownspot	0.99	1.00	0.99	581
	Healthy	1.00	0.90	0.94	580

	Hispa	0.94	1.00	0.97	582
	Leafblast	0.97	1.00	0.99	580
DCNN	Brownspot	0.99	1.00	0.99	581
	Healthy	1.00	0.95	0.97	580
	Hispa	0.97	1.00	0.98	582
	Leafblast	0.99	1.00	0.99	580

8. Conclusion

During the era Deep learning is in limelight as it is showing amazing results in many fields such as voice recognition, object detection and in agriculture as well. Detection of plant disease at their early stages is a challenging task, if they are not detected timely it may affect the quality and

productivity of crop. Whereas, Deep learning architectures are able to detect plant diseases at early stages so that damage can be avoided. In this research study comparative analysis of different pre-trained learning model is performed, transfer learning and fine tuning is applied on rice dataset.

Out of all the pre-trained models VGG16 accomplished highest accuracy 94%. To achieve more reliable and accurate results, two models i) SCNN based on CNN model and ii) DCNN based on pre trained VGG19 by freezing all layers . DCNN is trained on 3 fully connected layer and one output layer. DCNN achieve 99.88% training accuracy while SCNN achieve 98.11% training accu-

racy. Both the models accomplished good accuracy but DCNN accomplished a bit higher accuracy than SCNN. Both models predicted disease in an accurate manner. In future, this proposed methodology can be applied at more rice diseased classes for detection also this can be applied for other plants diseases as well. Other deep learning models such as RCNN can be used for rice disease detection as well. Moreover, these models can be compiled into robots as they can perform task in more efficient and diligent way without

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